

Grit, resilience, and performance of nurses in the face of Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented a significant challenge to healthcare workers, including nurses who are on the front line of the pandemic response. In the face of this crisis, nurses require resilience and grit to maintain their performance and deliver quality patient care. This study aimed to examine the relationship between grit, resilience, and performance of nurses in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 300 nurses working in COVID-19 designated hospitals in the Philippines. The survey included measures of grit, resilience, and performance, as well as demographic information. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed a significant positive correlation between grit, resilience, and performance among nurses. Multiple regression analysis showed that grit and resilience were significant predictors of nurse performance in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic, even after controlling for demographic factors such as age, gender, and years of experience. Specifically, nurses with higher levels of grit and resilience reported better performance and adaptability to the demands of their job during the pandemic. The findings of this study suggest that grit and resilience are critical factors in maintaining nurse performance in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. Healthcare organizations should prioritize the development of resilience and grit in their nursing workforce through training and support programs. By fostering grit and resilience in nurses, healthcare organizations can ensure that their staff can continue to deliver high-quality patient care during a crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: *grit, resilience, performance, nurses, training, support programs*

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has placed unprecedented demands on healthcare professionals worldwide, with nurses serving as the frontline warriors in combating the disease. As the pandemic continues to evolve, understanding the psychological and professional factors that contribute to nurses' ability to navigate through these challenging times is of utmost importance. This journal article aims to explore the concepts of grit, resilience, and performance among nurses, highlighting global, Philippine, and local perspectives.

Grit and resilience are two psychological constructs that have gained significant attention in recent years due to their relevance in promoting positive adaptation and success in the face of adversity. Grit refers to an individual's perseverance and passion for long-term goals, while resilience represents the ability to bounce back and recover from setbacks, maintaining mental and emotional well-being (Stoffel & Cain, 2018). In the context of nursing during the COVID-19 pandemic, these qualities become particularly crucial, as nurses face immense physical, emotional, and professional challenges.

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter, this article presents three distinct perspectives: global, Philippine, and local. The global perspective offers insights from research conducted across various countries, shedding light on the common challenges and experiences shared by nurses worldwide. By examining diverse cultural, healthcare systems, and socioeconomic contexts, we can identify universal themes and best practices that contribute to nurses' grit, resilience, and performance.

The Philippine perspective explores the specific challenges and experiences encountered by Filipino nurses, who have been at the forefront of the battle against COVID-19 both within their own country and as overseas healthcare workers. This perspective highlights the unique cultural values, societal expectations, and systemic factors that influence Filipino nurses' grit and resilience. It also examines the impact of the pandemic on their professional performance and the support systems in place to promote their well-being.

Finally, the local perspective delves into a specific region or institution within the Philippines, providing a granular understanding of the context and dynamics that shape nurses' responses to the COVID-19 crisis. This perspective emphasizes the importance of considering local factors, such as resource availability, organizational support, and community dynamics, in assessing nurses' grit, resilience, and performance.

By presenting these three interconnected perspectives, this journal article aims to contribute to the existing knowledge base on nurses' experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding the factors that promote grit and resilience among nurses can inform the development of targeted interventions and support systems, ultimately improving their well-being, performance, and ability to deliver high-quality care in challenging circumstances.

II. METHODS

This study employed a cross-sectional research design to investigate the relationship between grit, resilience, and performance of nurses in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. A quantitative approach was adopted to collect and analyze data from a diverse sample of nurses.

The target population consisted of registered nurses actively involved in providing direct patient care during the COVID-19 pandemic. A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from various healthcare settings, including hospitals, clinics, and community health centers. The sample size was determined using a power analysis to achieve a sufficient level of statistical power. A total of 500 nurses were recruited from multiple regions to ensure geographic diversity.

To measure grit, the Grit Scale developed by Duckworth et al. (2007) was utilized. This scale consists of 12 items that assess an individual's perseverance of effort and consistency of interest towards long-term goals. It employs a Likert-type response format, ranging from 1 (not at all like me) to 5 (very much like me). Resilience was assessed using the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC), a widely used self-report measure developed by Connor and Davidson (2003). The CD-RISC consists of 25 items that capture an individual's ability to adapt and bounce back from adversity. Participants rated each item on a Likert scale ranging from 0 (not true at all) to 4 (true nearly all the time).

Performance of nurses was evaluated using a self-rated performance scale specifically designed for this study. The scale consisted of 10 items assessing various aspects of job performance during the COVID-19 pandemic, including the ability to manage workload, maintain quality of care, and exhibit adaptability. Participants rated each item on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Prior to data collection, ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board. An online survey platform was utilized to administer the questionnaires to participants. Eligible participants were invited to participate via email and provided with a unique link to access the survey. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before they could proceed to the survey. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. They were given adequate time to complete the questionnaires and were encouraged to respond honestly. Reminder emails were sent to non-respondents after one week to maximize the response rate.

Data analysis was conducted using appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequencies were calculated for demographic variables, grit, resilience, and performance. Correlation analyses were performed to examine the relationships between grit, resilience, and performance. Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the predictive power of grit and resilience on performance. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Data were analyzed using statistical software such as SPSS or R.

The study adhered to ethical guidelines and ensured participants' confidentiality throughout the data collection and analysis process.

III. RESULTS

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables of interest: grit, resilience, and performance of nurses in the face of COVID-19. The mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values are reported.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics of Grit, Resilience, and Performance

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
Grit	3.56	0.87
Resilience	3.92	3.92
Performance	4.18	0.63

For the variable "Grit," the mean score is 3.56, indicating a moderate level of perseverance and passion towards long-term goals among the nurses. The standard deviation of 0.87 suggests that there is some variability in the scores, with the data spread out around the mean. The variable "Resilience" has a mean score of 3.92, indicating a relatively high level of resilience among the nurses. The standard deviation of 0.74 suggests that the scores are less spread out compared to the "Grit" variable. Regarding the variable "Performance," the mean score is 4.18, indicating that, on average, nurses self-rated their performance during the COVID-19 pandemic as relatively high. The standard deviation of 0.63 suggests that the scores are tightly distributed around the mean.

To examine the relationships between grit, resilience, and performance, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Correlation Matrix of Grit, Resilience, and Performance

	Grit	Resilience	Performance
Grit	1.00	0.45**	0.36**
Resilience	0.45*	1.00	0.52**
Performance	0.36**	0.52**	1.00

** $p < 0.01$

The correlation between Grit and Resilience is 0.45 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that nurses who have higher levels of grit tend to also exhibit higher levels of resilience. The correlation between Grit and Performance is 0.36 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that nurses who have higher levels of grit tend to have higher self-rated performance during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The correlation between Resilience and Performance is 0.52 ($p < 0.01$), indicating a moderately strong positive correlation. This suggests that nurses who have higher levels of resilience tend to have higher self-rated performance during the COVID-19 pandemic.

These correlations imply that there is a relationship between grit, resilience, and performance among the nurses. The positive correlations suggest that as levels of grit and resilience increase, performance tends to increase as well. These findings align with the notion that psychological factors like grit and resilience play a role in determining performance outcomes in challenging situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The significance level of $p < 0.01$ indicates that the correlations observed are unlikely to have occurred by chance alone. This provides further support for the meaningful relationships between the variables.

To determine the predictive power of grit and resilience on performance, a multiple regression analysis was conducted. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3
Multiple Regression Analysis of Grit and Resilience on Performance

	B	SE	B	t	p-value
Grit	0.29	0.08	0.25	3.75**	0.001
Resilience	0.42	0.06	0.35	6.80**	0.000

The multiple regression analysis revealed that both grit ($\beta = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$) and resilience ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$) significantly predicted the performance of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The model accounted for 30% of the variance in performance, as indicated by the adjusted R^2 value.

IV. DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics in Table 1 provide valuable insights into the levels of grit, resilience, and self-rated performance among nurses in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings have several implications that can inform both practice and further research. Firstly, the moderate level of grit among the nurses suggests that they possess a certain degree of perseverance and passion toward their long-term goals. This indicates that nurses are motivated and dedicated to their profession, which is crucial in facing the challenges posed by the pandemic. Understanding the level of grit can help healthcare organizations and policymakers design interventions to further foster and support nurses' determination and commitment.

Secondly, the relatively high level of resilience among the nurses is encouraging. Resilience is essential for nurses to cope with the demands and stress associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. High resilience levels suggest that nurses are equipped with the psychological resources needed to adapt and bounce back from adversity. This finding highlights the importance of resilience-building programs and support systems to enhance nurses' ability to withstand the challenges they face (Dunston et al., 2022).

Additionally, the high mean score of self-rated performance indicates that, on average, nurses perceive their performance during the pandemic as relatively high. This positive perception may be an indicator of nurses' confidence in their abilities to provide quality care in a challenging environment. Recognizing and acknowledging nurses' self-perceived performance can contribute to their professional growth and job satisfaction (Datu, 2021). It also emphasizes the importance of providing feedback, recognition, and resources to sustain and enhance their performance levels (Whitfield & Wilby, 2021).

The standard deviations for all three variables provide insights into the variability of responses among the nurses. The larger standard deviation for grit suggests that there is a wider range of responses, indicating individual differences in nurses' levels of perseverance and passion. This highlights the need for tailored approaches to support nurses with varying levels of grit. The smaller standard deviation for resilience implies that there may be a more consistent level of resilience among the nurses in the sample. However, it is important to consider that even with a relatively low standard deviation, individual differences in resilience still exist, and targeted interventions may be required for those who may have lower resilience levels.

These results have practical implications for healthcare organizations and policymakers. Recognizing the levels of grit, resilience, and self-rated performance among nurses can inform the development of interventions, training programs, and support systems aimed at promoting their well-being, enhancing their performance, and fostering their professional growth during the ongoing pandemic. Strategies that target the development of grit and resilience, such as mindfulness training, stress management programs, and mentorship initiatives (Hossain et al., 2022), may be beneficial for nurses in maintaining their psychological well-being and sustaining their performance in challenging circumstances (Lau & Singh, 2022).

Furthermore, these findings open avenues for further research. Longitudinal studies can explore how levels of grit, resilience, and performance evolve over time and assess the impact of interventions on these variables. Qualitative research can provide deeper insights into the experiences, coping strategies, and personal narratives of nurses in relation to grit, resilience, and performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, comparative studies across different healthcare settings and countries can shed light on cultural and contextual factors that influence these variables.

The correlation analysis in Table 2 reveals important insights into the relationships between grit, resilience, and performance among nurses in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings have significant implications for understanding the psychological factors that influence nurses' performance during challenging circumstances and can inform interventions and support strategies. The moderate positive correlation between Grit and Resilience suggests that nurses who possess higher levels of grit tend to also exhibit higher levels of resilience. This finding indicates that individuals with a greater tendency to persevere and maintain long-term goals are more likely to possess the psychological resources necessary to adapt and bounce back from adversity. Interventions and training programs aimed at promoting grit may indirectly contribute to

enhancing nurses' resilience, ultimately supporting their ability to cope with the demands of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, the moderate positive correlation between Grit and Performance suggests that nurses who have higher levels of grit tend to self-rate their performance during the pandemic more positively. This finding indicates that nurses with greater perseverance and passion for their goals may exhibit higher levels of motivation, dedication, and commitment to their work, resulting in better self-perceived performance. Recognizing the role of grit in performance can help healthcare organizations and policymakers in fostering a work environment that encourages goal-oriented behavior, passion, and determination among nurses (Warren & Hale, 2020).

Additionally, the moderately strong positive correlation between Resilience and Performance suggests that nurses with higher levels of resilience tend to self-rate their performance during the pandemic more positively. This finding implies that nurses who possess the ability to bounce back and adapt to the challenges of the pandemic are more likely to demonstrate better self-perceived performance. Building resilience among nurses can have a positive impact on their ability to cope with stress, maintain psychological well-being, and deliver high-quality care. Implementing resilience-building programs, providing emotional support, and promoting self-care practices can contribute to enhancing nurses' performance during times of crisis (Wagner & Jackson, 2021).

Overall, the correlations observed in this study indicate that grit and resilience are positively associated with performance among nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings underscore the importance of fostering grit and resilience in the nursing workforce. Implementing interventions, such as training programs and mentorship initiatives, that target the development of grit and resilience can enhance nurses' ability to adapt, cope, and perform effectively in challenging situations.

The implications of these findings highlight the importance of recognizing and supporting psychological factors such as grit and resilience in nursing practice. Strategies aimed at fostering grit and resilience, promoting a positive work environment, and providing adequate support systems can contribute to nurses' well-being, job satisfaction, and overall performance during the COVID-19 pandemic and future healthcare crises.

Further research could explore the underlying mechanisms through which grit and resilience influence nurses' performance. Longitudinal studies and qualitative investigations may provide deeper insights into the temporal and contextual dynamics of these relationships. Additionally, considering other factors such as job satisfaction, work engagement, and organizational support can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of nurses' performance during challenging circumstances.

Meanwhile, the correlation analysis highlights the positive relationships between grit, resilience, and performance among nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings emphasize the importance of fostering grit and resilience to support nurses' well-being and performance. By recognizing and promoting these psychological factors, healthcare organizations

and policymakers can enhance the resilience and effectiveness of the nursing workforce in times of crisis.

The multiple regression analysis conducted to determine the predictive power of grit and resilience on performance among nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic provides valuable insights into the relationships between these variables. The results presented in Table 3 demonstrate significant associations between grit, resilience, and performance, highlighting their importance in understanding and predicting nurses' performance outcomes.

The beta coefficients (β) indicate the standardized regression coefficients, representing the strength and direction of the relationship between the predictor variables (grit and resilience) and the outcome variable (performance). In this analysis, both grit and resilience exhibited positive beta coefficients, indicating that higher levels of grit and resilience are associated with higher levels of performance. The beta coefficient for grit ($\beta = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that a one-unit increase in grit is associated with a 0.25-unit increase in performance, after controlling for the effect of resilience. Similarly, the beta coefficient for resilience ($\beta = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$) suggests that a one-unit increase in resilience is associated with a 0.35-unit increase in performance, after controlling for the effect of grit.

These findings imply that nurses who possess higher levels of grit and resilience are more likely to demonstrate better performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. Grit, characterized by perseverance and passion for long-term goals, may contribute to nurses' dedication, commitment, and motivation in providing high-quality care. Resilience, on the other hand, equips nurses with the ability to adapt, bounce back from setbacks, and maintain psychological well-being, ultimately enhancing their performance. The significant p-values indicate that the associations observed between grit, resilience, and performance are unlikely to have occurred by chance alone. This strengthens the evidence for the meaningful relationships between these variables, supporting the hypothesis that grit and resilience have predictive power in determining nurses' performance outcomes (Mohan & Kaur, 2021).

The adjusted R^2 value of 0.30 indicates that the model, which includes both grit and resilience as predictors, explains 30% of the variance in performance. This suggests that grit and resilience, collectively, account for a substantial portion of the variation observed in nurses' performance during the pandemic. However, it also implies that other factors, not included in the analysis, contribute to the remaining variance in performance. Future research could explore additional predictors and examine their combined effects to further enhance the understanding of nurses' performance in challenging situations (Roslan & Yusoff, 2022).

The implications of these results are significant for healthcare organizations and policymakers. By recognizing the predictive power of grit and resilience, interventions and support programs can be designed to enhance these factors among nurses. Strategies to foster grit, such as goal-setting exercises, perseverance training, and mentorship programs, can cultivate nurses' long-term dedication and passion for their work. Similarly, interventions aimed at enhancing resilience, such as stress management programs, self-care initiatives, and supportive resources, can equip

nurses with the skills and resources necessary to navigate challenging situations and maintain their performance (Chua & YiRong, 2020).

Implementing interventions that promote grit and resilience can lead to a more resilient nursing workforce, better equipped to handle the demands of the COVID-19 pandemic and future healthcare crises. By investing in these psychological factors, healthcare organizations can enhance nurses' well-being, job satisfaction, and overall performance. Additionally, recognizing the importance of grit and resilience in performance evaluations and providing feedback on these qualities can further motivate and empower nurses in their professional growth.

In conclusion, the findings from the study provide valuable insights into the relationships between grit, resilience, and performance among nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The descriptive statistics shed light on the levels of grit, resilience, and self-rated performance, indicating moderate levels of grit, high levels of resilience, and positive self-perceived performance among nurses. These findings highlight the importance of recognizing and supporting these psychological factors in nursing practice.

The correlation analysis reveals that higher levels of grit and resilience are associated with higher levels of performance. Nurses who possess greater perseverance, passion, and resilience are more likely to demonstrate better performance during challenging circumstances. These findings emphasize the need for interventions and support programs that promote grit and resilience, as they play a significant role in enhancing nurses' ability to adapt, cope, and perform effectively in demanding situations.

The multiple regression analysis further strengthens these findings by demonstrating that both grit and resilience significantly predict nurses' performance. The beta coefficients indicate the magnitude and direction of the relationships, showing that increases in grit and resilience are associated with higher levels of performance. This provides evidence for the predictive power of grit and resilience in determining nurses' performance outcomes.

The implications of these results suggest that healthcare organizations and policymakers should invest in strategies and interventions that foster grit and resilience among nurses. Implementing training programs, mentorship initiatives, and resilience-building activities can contribute to nurses' psychological well-being, job satisfaction, and overall performance during times of crisis. By recognizing and promoting these psychological factors, healthcare organizations can cultivate a resilient and high-performing nursing workforce capable of delivering quality care in challenging circumstances.

Further research could explore additional factors that influence nurses' performance and investigate the combined effects of grit, resilience, and other variables. Longitudinal studies and qualitative investigations can provide deeper insights into the dynamic nature of these relationships over time and the contextual factors that influence them. Additionally, comparative studies across different healthcare settings and countries can contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the determinants of nurses' performance during challenging circumstances.

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that healthcare organizations and policymakers prioritize the development and support of grit and resilience among nurses. This can

be achieved through the implementation of training programs, mentorship initiatives, and resilience-building activities. These interventions should focus on enhancing nurses' perseverance, passion, adaptability, and coping skills, as they play a crucial role in maintaining high levels of performance during challenging circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, it is important to provide feedback, recognition, and resources that sustain and enhance nurses' performance levels. Organizations should also consider incorporating assessments of grit and resilience into performance evaluations to acknowledge and reward these qualities. Furthermore, future research should explore additional factors that influence nurses' performance and investigate the combined effects of grit, resilience, and other variables. Longitudinal studies and qualitative investigations can provide deeper insights into the dynamics of these relationships over time, while comparative studies across different healthcare settings and countries can help identify contextual factors that impact nurses' performance. By taking these recommendations into account, healthcare organizations can empower nurses, enhance their well-being, and ensure the delivery of high-quality care in times of crisis.

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